

In Brief

Unsustainable Practice of Juvenile Hilsa Catch in West Bengal

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Hilsa fish are prevalently caught during the monsoon season. During the first week of rains, premature fishing leads to netting of juvenile hilsa and subsequently the market is filled with juvenile Hilsa fish, each weighing around 200g. This year, in 2023, the monsoon rains were late in arrival. The meteorological department had forecasted an estimated arrival date of 10 June. However, the monsoon rains got further delayed and 20 June was officially acknowledged as the date of arrival of monsoon in the state of West Bengal, India.

For the first time, fisher caught 200 metric tons of juvenile Hilsa fish in their nets in the fishing season of 2023. If fishermen catch too many Hilsa that are still in infantile stage, Hilsa fish may be lost prematurely in the estuarine region of the Sunderbans. Fertile juvenile Hilsa fish caught in the nets of fishermen and not released will never get the chance to come to fresh water to lay eggs. The effect of this is noticeable in the Hilsa production of West Bengal. The numbers of Hilsa fish are not increasing in any way. Moreover, 30 metric tons of juvenile Hilsa caught in Namkhana and Kakdwip fish harbours at the beginning of 2023 were sold off at the wholesale market of Nagendra Bazar in Diamond Harbour. One day the going price was ₹ 137-185 per kg, but the next day, at the same place, the Hilsa was being sold for ₹ 300-350 per kg. The fish traders are more than happy to sale immature (and small) Hilsa, because they can rake in massive profits with very little investment. The middle-class residents of Kolkata buy this fish from the fish markets. Such practices are especially prevalent in Behala, Thakurpukur, Tollygunge, Kasba, and even Manicktala. Shoppers usually return home

with 2-3 pieces of fish each. Such incidents of sale of juvenile Hilsa have worried marine scientists. Although the fishermen catch this juvenile Hilsa, the fish traders' association does not condone this fishing in any way or form. The association also knowledgeable about the adverse effects of catching immature Hilsa, stated in the words of the representatives of the association: if juvenile Hilsa is caught before their time of egg laying, there is no possibility of further Hilsa breeding. In light of such a situation, the government has advised the use of large nets (fishing nets with larger holes) to prevent catching juvenile Hilsa. By using the right size net, smaller Hilsa can pass through the net and only mature Hilsa will get caught. Several years ago, the West Bengal state government banned the sale of juvenile Hilsa fish caught in the Sunderbans. On the other side of the border, the governing body of Bangladesh has implemented strict repercussions for catching and selling immature Hilsa. Individuals are imprisoned for 1-2 years and fined up to Tk 5000. However, no such legislation has been enforced in West Bengal. As there is no disciplinary action, the quantity of Hilsa caught in the estuary of West Bengal exhibits a decreasing trend (Table 1).

Table 1. Annual variations of hilsa catch in the estuarine region of West Bengal

Year	Mature Hilsa Catch (metric ton)
2003	62,000
2011	59,000
2014	45,000
2017	10,000
2022	20,000

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